

Disclosure of Future Information and Its Impact on Profit Quality: An Empirical Study of a Sample of Companies Listed on the Iraq Stock Exchange

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Abstract

The aim of this research is to examine the impact of disclosing future information on earnings quality among a sample of companies listed on the Iraq Stock Exchange. The study seeks to test the effect of the level of disclosure of future information on the company's earnings quality. To achieve the research objective, an empirical study was conducted on a sample of companies listed on the Iraq Stock Exchange, covering the period from 2019 to 2023. The research findings include several key results, most notably: a significant positive impact of the level of disclosure of future information on earnings quality. The research also provides several recommendations for the companies studied, with the most important being the need to strengthen the role of both internal and external audits in verifying the credibility of future information, thus enhancing earnings quality.

Keywords: *Disclosure of Future Information, Earnings Quality, stock exchange, audit.*

JEL Classification codes: *D53, M41, M42.*

Suggested citation: Mahdi, N.A., Khalid, R.W., & Zaidan, A.M. (2025). Disclosure of Future Information and Its Impact on Profit Quality: An Empirical Study of a Sample of Companies Listed on the Iraq Stock Exchange. *European Journal of Management, Economics and Business*, 2(3), 142-153. DOI: 10.59324/ejmec.2025.2(3).11

Introduction

Accounting thought has given significant importance to accounting disclosure due to its prominent role in the financial market. The decisions made by market participants are based on the information disclosed by companies. The financial reports prepared by companies reflect their financial performance; therefore, these reports must contain all the information that reflects the companies' performance and their ability to continue in the long term.

Due to the developments in the business environment, there is a growing need for the development and expansion of disclosure, which no longer relies solely on mandatory disclosure but extends to

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voluntary disclosure as well. Accounting disclosure of future information is considered one of the essential elements of voluntary disclosure. Studies have highlighted the importance of disclosing future information to reduce the phenomenon of information asymmetry, thus helping management in making informed decisions and improving earnings quality. Additionally, voluntary disclosure is a fundamental and vital element in ensuring the rights of investors and shareholders, as it enhances trust among stakeholders, positively influencing the company's overall performance, reputation, and the transparency of both its financial and non-financial reports (Hamdan, et al., 2023). Therefore, users require new and clear information, which leads to attracting them and improving their earnings quality.

Methodology

Research Problem

Due to the global developments and the increasing intensity of competition between companies, many companies have failed to fully and adequately disclose both financial and non-financial information to attract investors. As a result, company management has resorted to manipulating certain accounting methods and procedures to present their profits in a more favorable light to stakeholders. This lack of transparency often leads to the collapse of many global companies. To address this issue, the following question arises: What impact does the disclosure of future information have on the quality of earnings for industrial companies listed on the Iraq Stock Exchange?

Importance of Research

The significance of this research lies in its focus on the study variable that the researcher seeks to address, which motivated the search for solutions. The study's importance stems from its focus on a contemporary and crucial topic both scientifically and practically. Practically, the study contributes by providing an explanation of the reasons and economic effects of the demand for disclosing future information on the quality of earnings. Scientifically, this study extends accounting research that has focused on exploring the complementary relationship between the study variables and enhancing earnings quality through the disclosure of future information.

Research Objectives

Given the nature and importance of the problem, the primary objective of this study is to examine the effect of disclosing future information on the quality of earnings. This will be achieved by conducting an applied study of a sample of companies listed on the Iraq Stock Exchange. The study also includes the following sub-objectives:

1. To provide a theoretical framework for the study variables, particularly within the Iraqi environment, and to define the concept of disclosing future information.
2. To clarify the concept of earnings quality and identify the factors that influence it.

Research Hypotheses

In order to answer the main research question, which represents the problem the researcher seeks to find logical solutions for, the following hypothesis has been formulated:

Disclosing future information has a statistically significant effect on the quality of earnings for industrial companies listed on the Iraq Stock Exchange.

Research Boundaries

The boundaries of the research are as follows:

Spatial Boundaries: The research is limited to a sample of Iraqi companies from various sectors listed on the Iraq Stock Exchange.

Temporal Boundaries: The temporal boundaries of the research are based on financial reports and statements covering the period from 2019 to 2023.

Research Methodology

Two research methods were employed in the study: the inductive method, which used books, scientific journals and theses; and the descriptive analytical method, which was used to achieve the study's objective. The descriptive analytical method is the most commonly used approach to studying social and human phenomena, and is therefore well suited to the topic of the current study.

Figure 1. The Study Variables

Source: Figure prepared by the researchers

Theoretical Framework of Study Variables and Their Relationship

The Concept of Disclosure of Future Information

Accounting disclosure is one of the fundamental elements in the financial market as it involves presenting all information through which stakeholders can make informed decisions. Given the importance of future information, this topic has been widely debated both professionally and academically (Adel, 2023: 9). Menicucci (2017: 102) added that the disclosure of accounting information is of significant importance to both academics and professionals, and academics define it as information provided either in a financial format or in the form of items. Future information is prepared to assist management in decision-making.

Accordingly, the researchers believe that the disclosure of future information involves companies revealing expected information that may include financial, non-financial, economic, and scientific data. This information is characterized by its subjectivity, as it depends on personal judgment and assumptions that are likely to occur in the future.

The Importance of Disclosure of Future Information

Many studies have addressed the importance of disclosing future information, as it provides several benefits to company management, including reducing risks related to stock return fluctuations, improving stock liquidity, and increasing the market value of the stock. Additionally, it reduces the

cost of capital required by investors and lenders to mitigate the risk of insufficient information. Furthermore, it provides a positive signal about the company's ability to enhance competition, attract investors, and strengthen its reputation in the market (Alqatamin et al., 2017: 2). It was also noted that disclosing future information reduces information asymmetry between stakeholders and company management, helping them make informed decisions and strengthening stakeholders' confidence in the company's future performance, which supports relationships with them (Nuji, 2023: 287).

As can be seen from the above, disclosing financial and non-financial information increases transparency. While company management is not obligated to disclose such information, it voluntarily provides it to meet the needs of its users and relevant parties, thereby enhancing the company's position in the capital market in the long term.

Motivations and Reasons for Disclosing Future Information

Several researchers have categorized the motivations and reasons for disclosing future information (Bravo, 2016: 3; Al-Daem, 2019: 340), the most important of which are as follows:

1. Increasing Company Value

Disclosing positive information leads to an increase in the company's value. Managers are motivated to disclose such information to distinguish the company from others, leading to an increase in demand for the company's shares and consequently, a rise in its market value.

2. Reducing Information Asymmetry

Disclosing management's expectations of future information enhances a company's ability to attract new capital. Some argue that disclosing future information reduces information asymmetry, improves decision-making processes, enhances opportunities for external financing, and reduces its cost.

3. Litigation Costs

Investors and shareholders may sue companies for failing to disclose important future information in a timely manner. Such lawsuits decrease as the quality of disclosure increases, boosting investor and lender confidence, which positively reflects on management quality and earnings quality.

4. Attracting New Capital

Disclosing future information is an essential element companies can use to secure financing by building a good reputation with stakeholders and increasing their confidence in the company. This helps companies obtain loans and issue shares and bonds, thus increasing capital and reducing the cost of capital.

The Concept of Earnings Quality

The concept of earnings quality has expanded according to various modern literatures and studies. In accounting thought, earnings quality is viewed from two perspectives. The first perspective focuses on decision usefulness and emphasizes the benefit of decision-making. (Oglove) was the first to introduce the concept of earnings quality and wrote about investment and advisory reports, describing earnings quality in terms of sustainability, though he did not provide a specific definition. The second perspective is economic in nature and suggests that earnings quality can be achieved through aligning the economic and accounting concepts of income (Rashid et al., 2022: 57). According to Al-Snidi et al. (2022: 191), the concept of earnings quality varies depending on the stakeholders benefiting from the financial statements. Some consider the sustainability of earnings as a sign of their quality, while others argue that earnings quality is defined by the truthfulness and

accuracy of the reported earnings, in alignment with generally accepted accounting principles. The more credible the earnings, free from manipulation, the higher their quality.

Researchers note that earnings quality is a crucial aspect in assessing a company's financial position. It can be achieved by evaluating the extent to which current earnings can be sustained in future periods. The more sustainable the earnings, the higher the level of earnings quality.

Importance of Earnings Quality

The importance of accounting earnings quality stems from the significance of earnings themselves. Hatem et al. (2021: 241) defined the importance of earnings quality as reflecting the true earnings of companies and its role in forecasting future earnings. Therefore, it is considered one of the key indicators for dividend distributions and an important factor to consider when making investment decisions. Ashoul (2021: 11) added the following points regarding the importance of earnings quality:

1. It is an important indicator that reduces the risk of information asymmetry in companies.
2. It helps reduce deficits and cases of financial collapse.
3. Earnings quality provides protection for users of financial reports from earnings management practices.
4. It increases the ability of lenders and creditors to assess a company's ability to meet its obligations, which helps maintain long-term relationships with the economic unit.
5. It increases the availability of financial information needed to assess, guide, and improve the company's financial performance.

Factors Affecting Earnings Quality

Several studies have highlighted factors influencing earnings quality (Al-Dulaimi, 2022: 76; Al-Ajrami, 2023: 40):

1. Board of Directors' Influence on Earnings Quality

It has been confirmed that there is a positive relationship between the number of board members and earnings quality. As the number of board members increases, the likelihood of earnings management also increases, which leads to a decrease in earnings quality due to manipulation in the financial statements prepared by the companies.

2. Quality of Accounting Standards

The application of both international and local accounting standards in preparing financial reports reduces the management's ability to engage in earnings management, thereby increasing the quality of earnings.

3. Shareholder Control

In socialist-oriented countries, where government ownership dominates, the percentage of shareholder control is higher, leading to lower earnings quality in these companies. When shareholder control falls below half, it results in a decrease in earnings quality.

Earnings Quality Measures

There are several widely used measures of earnings quality in accounting research (Al-Ajrami, 2023: 40; Adel, 2022: 472), the most important of which are as follows:

1. Quality of Accruals

Accruals are defined as the difference between net income and operating cash flows. They arise when there is a timing difference between the occurrence of cash flows and the accounting recognition of financial transactions carried out by companies during the fiscal year.

2. Earnings Sustainability

This refers to the extent to which current profits will continue in future years. The more sustainable a company's earnings are, the higher their quality.

3. Predictive Ability of Earnings

Earnings' ability to improve the ability of financial statement users to predict related items. The higher the earnings' predictive ability, the higher the quality of the company's future earnings.

The Relationship Between Disclosing Future Information and Earnings Quality

Due to developments taking place both domestically and globally, there has been an increasing need to disclose future information and its importance in providing financial and non-financial information, which can enhance trust between stakeholders and companies' performance. It also reduces information asymmetry, helping stakeholders make decisions that enable them to gain a broader understanding of the company's operations and evaluate the quality of its earnings. A study by Brahmana et al. (2018) found that environmental disclosure has a positive impact on earnings quality, while Aghai et al. (2023) added that there is no statistically significant relationship between the level of disclosure of future information and the future profitability of companies. Furthermore, studies by Noji (2023) and Waweru et al. (2016) indicated a consensus in many previous studies on the positive impact of the level of disclosure of future information (both financial and non-financial) on companies' future financial performance. Additionally, Al-Ajrami (2023) pointed out that voluntary disclosure has a positive effect on the quality of earnings disclosed in the financial statements listed on the Palestine Stock Exchange, and it was found that the level of voluntary disclosure in the financial sector is greater than that in the non-financial sector in terms of voluntary disclosure items. Liao et al. (2023) argued that managers who disclose future earnings forecasts attract investors strongly, although the quality of that information may not necessarily be of the same high quality. However, the market response linked to these forecasts supports the existence of a positive relationship between the disclosure of information and earnings quality.

Research Population

The research population comprises a group of Iraqi companies that are listed on the Iraq Stock Exchange. The sample includes five different sectors in the market, which are the most relevant for the study. This sample was randomly selected based on a set of conditions:

The company should not have incurred consecutive losses for two consecutive years.

The company's financial reports should be available in chronological order for the duration of the study.

Sources of Data Collection

The researchers relied on two primary sources to gather the necessary information to achieve the study's results and objectives:

1. Secondary Sources

The researchers relied on literature review from books, scientific journals, academic theses, articles, and research from both Arabic and international websites. This was done to clarify the basic concepts addressed in the study. The study aims to provide results that can benefit researchers and

official entities interested in regulating the Iraq Stock Exchange's operations, especially in setting an accounting standard that governs the disclosure of future information.

2. Primary Sources

To measure the level of disclosure about future information in Iraqi companies listed on the Iraq Stock Exchange, the researchers used an index consisting of a set of elements indicating future information that companies may disclose. These elements were divided into three groups: (1) Information related to strategic goals, (2) Future financial information, (3) Future non-financial information).

Results and Discussion

The future projection of any financial variable is defined as follows:

$$E[Yt] = f(X1, X2, \dots, Xn) + \epsilon t \quad (1)$$

Where:

$E[Yt]$ – Expected value of the future variable at time (e.g., revenues, profits, or cash flows):

X_1, X_2, \dots, X_n : A set of input variables or basic assumptions (such as market prices, cost of capital, demand growth, etc.).

Forecasting function or model used for prediction:

(e.g., regression model or time-series model).

ϵ_t : Random error or margin of uncertainty related to the forecast at time t.

To measure profit quality:

The return on assets ratio, calculated by dividing the company's net profit before tax by total assets.

$$ROA_{i,t+1} = \beta_0 + \beta_1(ROA_{i,t} - TACC_{i,t}) + \beta_2TACC_{i,t} + l_{it} \quad (2)$$

Where:

$ROA_{i,t+1}$ = Return on Assets (ROA) of the company for the current period

β_1 = Continuity of cash flows

β_2 = Continuity of accruals

$TACC_{i,t}$ = Total accruals of the company for the current year

l_{it} = Estimation error

Table 1. The Companies Listed in the Iraq Stock Exchange Index

S	Company Name	Company Code
1	AsiaCell	TASC
2	Al-Mamoura Real Estate	SMRI

3	Baghdad Iraq Public Transport	SBPT
4	Chemical Industries	INCP
5	Agricultural Products Marketing	AIRP

Source: Prepared by the researchers based on the annual reports of companies listed on the Iraq Stock Exchange

Testing the Normal Distribution of the Study Data

In order to use statistical techniques, it is first necessary to determine whether the collected data follow a normal distribution. If the data are normally distributed, parametric tests can be used to test the hypotheses (Al-Kilidar, 2009). If not, non-parametric tests should be employed. In interpreting the test results, if the observed significance level (p-value) is greater than 0.05, the observed distribution is considered to be the same as the theoretical distribution, indicating that the data follow a normal distribution (Parsons, 2025). However, if the p-value is less than 0.05, the observed distribution differs from the expected distribution, indicating that the data do not follow a normal distribution (Al-Khazraji, & Al-Khazraji, 2023).

This test examines the validity of the data according to the following hypotheses:

H₀: The observed and expected frequencies are the same (normal distribution).

H₁: The observed and expected frequencies differ (non-normal distribution).

Table 2. Normality Test

Variables	Level of Significance	Error Value	Result
Strategic Objectives	0.075	0.05	Normal
Forward-looking Financial Information	0.123	0.05	Normal
Forward-looking Non-Financial Information	0.163	0.05	Normal
Earnings Quality	0.175	0.05	Normal
Profitability	0.115	0.05	Normal
Return on Assets (ROA)	0.120	0.05	Normal

Source: Prepared by the researcher based on Excel software

Descriptive Statistics Results

Table 2 provides a summary of the variables included in the study used to test the hypothesis. These variables include the extent to which forward-looking information is disclosed and the quality of earnings. The table shows the mean, standard deviation, maximum and minimum values observed for each variable during the study period (2019–2023), based on a total of 720 observations.

Table 3. Descriptive Statistics Results for the Study Variables

Variables	Year	Mean	Standard Deviation	Maximum Value	Minimum Value
Disclosure of Forward-Looking Information	2019	0.311	0.101	0,444	0,097
	2020	0.324	0.149	0,434	0,120
	2021	0,334	0.128	0.343	0,132
	2022	0,320	0.169	0,522	0,054
	2023	0,322	0.109	0,501	0,078
Earnings Quality	2019	0,154	0.150	0,254	0.001-
	2020	0,155	0.205	0,355	0.001-

	2021	0,142	0.184	0,172	0.003
	2022	0,132	0.186	0,232	0.046
	2023	0,145	0.105	0,195	0,005

Source: Prepared by the researchers based on Excel software

As can be seen in Table 3, the level of forward-looking information disclosure among Iraqi companies listed on the Iraq Stock Exchange (the study sample) is generally low. The highest average level was recorded in 2021 at only 0.334%, which is considered low. This corresponds with the highest value for that year of 0.343%, with a standard deviation of 0.128.

The main reason for the low level of disclosure of forward-looking information by listed companies is the absence of an accounting standard that regulates the disclosure process and how such information is prepared. There is also no mandatory requirement for companies to disclose a minimum set of forward-looking information elements. As a result, disclosure is voluntary and left to the discretion of each company.

Regarding earnings quality, the highest value was recorded in 2020 at 0.355%, with a mean of 0.155 and a standard deviation of 0.205.

Hypothesis Testing

1. Testing the correlation between forward-looking information disclosure and accounting earnings quality

Table 4. Correlation Between Forward-Looking Information Disclosure and Accounting Earnings Quality

	Forward-Looking Information			Overall Index
	Strategic Objectives	Future Financial Information	Non-Financial Future Information	
Accounting Earnings Quality	0.069	0.045*	0.099*	0.0321*
Sig	0.115	0.026	0.033	0.035

Note: (*) Significant relationship at the level of (0.05)

Source: Prepared by the researchers using EViews software

As can be seen from Table 4, it is clear that the correlation between forward-looking information (strategic objectives) and accounting earnings quality is weak. However, there is a significant positive relationship between future financial and non-financial information and earnings quality.

Table 5. The Correlation between Forward-Looking Information and Accounting Earnings

	Disclosure of future information	sig
Earnings quality	0.0321*	0.035

Note: (*) Statistically significant at the (0.05) level

Source: Prepared by the researcher based on EViews software

The test of the first hypothesis, which indicates a statistically significant positive correlation at the 0.05 significance level between the disclosure of future information as the independent variable and accounting earnings quality as the dependent variable, shows that the total correlation coefficient value is (0.321) at a significance level of (0.035), which is less than (5). This value indicates a positive correlation between the disclosure of future information and accounting earnings quality at the overall level in the surveyed companies. This result is consistent with the theoretical section of the study, which clarified the role of disclosing future information in enhancing the accounting earnings quality issued by companies, and with studies (Nweji, 2023; Waweru, 2016) regarding the positive impact of the level of future information disclosure on financial performance and earnings quality.

ANOVA Analysis and Regression Model Coefficients at the Overall Level

Table 6. ANOVA Analysis and Regression Model Coefficients at the Overall Level

MODEL	Unstandardized Coefficients		Beta	R2	T	Sig	F	Sig
	B	Std.Err.						
A constant	0.088	0.426	0.054	0.142	0.231	0.752	2.132	0.035

Source: Prepared by the researcher based on EViews software

As shown in Table 6, the results of the analysis indicate that there is a statistically significant direct effect of disclosing future information on accounting earnings quality. The calculated F-value was (2.132) at a significance level of (0.035), which is less than (5%), indicating the validity of the regression used to test the effect of future information disclosure on accounting earnings quality. As for the Beta coefficient, it was (0.054), which indicates that a one-unit change in the variable of future information disclosure leads to a change in accounting earnings quality by (0.054). Meanwhile, the constant regression coefficient (BO) was a positive value of (0.088), with a standard error (Std. Error) of (0.426).

Table 7. ANOVA Analysis and Regression Model Coefficients at the Overall Level

MODEL	Unstandardized Coefficients		Beta	R2	T	Sig	F	Sig
	B	Std.Err.						
Strategic Objectives	0.097	0.326	0,212	0.212	2.156	0.00	6.188	0.015
Future Financial Information	0.180	0.406	0,150	0.195	3.145	0.00	5.221	0.045
Non-Financial Future Information	0.280	0.226	0,245	0.202	4.034	0.00	5.123	0.026

Source: Prepared by the researchers based on the EViews software.

It is clear from Table 7 that there is a weak impact of some disclosure mechanisms on future information, as the regression coefficient value for strategic objectives was (0.212), while the regression coefficient value for non-financial future information was (0.245), indicating a positive significant effect of future financial information and the size of the board of directors on the quality of accounting profits.

Based on the data above, it is evident that there is a positive correlation between the disclosure of future information and the quality of accounting profits. Furthermore, a direct statistically

significant impact is observed between the disclosure of future information in Iraqi companies listed in the stock market.

Conclusions

The study led to several conclusions in both the theoretical and practical aspects, with the key findings being:

The results show that disclosing information directly contributes to increasing transparency in financial reports, which positively impacts the quality of profits.

A positive correlation exists, indicating that the disclosure of future information helps investors and analysts evaluate the future performance of companies more accurately, thereby increasing the validity and credibility of the disclosed financial results.

Increased disclosure of future expectations reduces the chances of earnings manipulation due to the increased control measures and enhanced accuracy in performance forecasts.

A statistically significant positive impact of future financial information and board size on the quality of accounting profits was found.

Recommendations

Based on the conclusions of the research, the researchers recommend the following:

1. It is essential for companies to provide accurate and systematic future information within their financial reports to support the quality of profits.
2. Clear and organized standards should be established to ensure consistency and comparability across companies, i.e., developing a regulatory framework for disclosure.
3. Increasing investor awareness to enhance their understanding of how to analyze future information and link it to profit quality.
4. Strengthening the role of both internal and external audits to verify the credibility of future information, which would, in turn, enhance the quality of profits.

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